

Asymmetric exchange rate pass-through: Evidence from major countries.

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to investigate the asymmetric effect of exchange rate variations on prices over the short- and long-run. To this end, we estimate a mark-up model for prices using a novel and simple asymmetric cointegrating model, with positive and negative partial sum decomposition of the nominal exchange rates. Our results show that prices react differently to appreciations and depreciations over the long-run, an effect that was previously ignored in the literature. In particular, we provide evidence that depreciations are passed through prices more than appreciations, a result that might suggest weak competition structures. This result has important implications for the proper conduct of monetary policy.

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1 Introduction

Understanding the form and the scale in which nominal exchange rate changes are passed through to domestic prices is an important issue from a central bank perspective that has an objective of price stabilization. Even more, from an international perspective, the exchange rate pass-through (ERPT) determines the level of real exchange rates, a key determinant of the adjustment pattern of the balance of payment.

Until recently, the existing empirical research assumed that there is a symmetric long-run relationship between the price level and the exchange rate. It was presumed that appreciations and depreciations are transmitted in the same magnitude to the final price. However, asymmetries are widely observed in the prices of final goods and they are mostly explained by rigidities, implying that prices are more sticky downwards than they are upwards. These rigidities make the hypothesis of a symmetric pass-through unrealistic and too restrictive. In fact omitting asymmetric effects of exchange rates on prices may seriously distort the effects of monetary policies.

As a consequence, in a new strand of the empirical literature, the standard assumption of a symmetric ERPT is relaxed. For example, Peltzman (2000) studies over 240 markets for consumer as well as producer goods and finds that asymmetries are pervasive, substantial and durable, and exist in periods of low inflation as well as in periods of high inflation¹.

Remarkably, in the recent empirical literature that relaxes the symmetry hypothesis, the estimations are run in log difference equations. Yet using the first differences of the data to remove persistence leads to omission of essential information. In addition, the evidence that consumer prices and exchange rates are cointegrated is well established in linear estimations (Mishkin (2008)).

In this paper, we go further than the previous literature by adopting a nonlinear cointegrating specification. We investigate the response of the CPI to exchange rate changes in four major developed countries (Germany, Japan, the United States and the United Kingdom), during the 1980-2009 period. Our methodology is based on a nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) model,

¹See, also, Mahdavi (2002), Pollard and Coughlin (2003), Campa and Sebastián-Barriol (2006), Yang (2007), Bussière (2007).

that has the enviable advantage of allowing for long- and/or short-run asymmetry. More precisely, the NARDL, proposed by Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011), consists in a dynamic error correction representation associated with the asymmetric long-run cointegrating regression. Three restricted specifications are obtained by imposing the long- and the short-run symmetry restrictions separately or jointly. The resulting empirical model includes elements of the asymmetric response of the price level and inflation to exchange rate changes. In sum, our model offers a proper specification that takes into account both the cointegration relationship between prices and the exchange rate and asymmetric effects. In addition, it captures long-run effects that were ignored in the previous literature estimated in first differences only (as Pollard and Coughlin (2003) or Bussière (2007), for instance).

Our estimations provide two results useful for the proper conduct of monetary policy. First, in all the countries under study, depreciations are passed through more often than are appreciations either in the long or in the short run, a result that might suggest weak competition structures and price stickiness. Second, the estimated value of the pass-through within the asymmetric model is significant and higher than in linear estimations. Indeed, a salient result of the recent empirical literature is the widespread decline in ERPT over the recent period. Several studies estimate that the average pass-through to consumer prices in developed economies is close to zero. This conclusion that exchange-rate movements have no noticeable impact on consumer prices has been very influential for determining the appropriate monetary policy response to exchange rate variations. The fact that our estimations yield higher ERPT values suggests that symmetric estimations have underestimated the real impact of exchange rate variations.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the arguments to relax the restricting assumption of a symmetric relationship between prices and the exchange rate and summarizes the results of the few related empirical studies. The methodology is described in Section 3. Section 4 briefly presents the data. The results regarding the estimation of the symmetric and asymmetric ARDL models are presented in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 offers some concluding remarks.

2 Asymmetric pass-through

This section reviews the arguments that suggest that the restricting symmetry assumption needs to be relaxed. Only a few empirical works have examined this issue. We present their findings at the end of this section.

2.1 Theoretical arguments

It is well established that an incomplete pass-through results from the strategic interaction between firms in an imperfect competition framework (see, for example, Krugman (1986)). Indeed, under imperfect competition, suppliers have a degree of market power, and they set their prices by taking the demands of consumers into account (Dixit and Stiglitz (1977)). The original pricing-to-market and mark-up models assumed that price-setting occurs in a symmetric manner after exchange rate variations. However, the decision to absorb or pass the exchange rate variations through to prices has opposite implications on the mark-up level regardless of if it is an appreciation or a depreciation. Indeed, whereas an appreciation of the domestic currency reduces the price of imported inputs, a depreciation increases these prices. Therefore, absorbing an appreciation (i.e., keeping the final price of the goods constant), has a positive effect on the seller's mark-up. On the contrary, keeping the final price of the goods constant after a depreciation of the domestic currency reduces the seller's mark-up. In general, the incentive to pass a depreciation through is higher in the case of an appreciation.

Obviously, the competitive structure is an influential determinant of the seller's decision. On the one hand, the higher the firm's market share and market power in the destination country, the lower the incentive to reduce margins and hence pass through nominal appreciations (Bussière (2007)). A firm in an oligopolistic position will therefore adjust its prices more during a depreciation than during an appreciation. On the contrary, in a competitive environment, producers may decide to absorb a depreciation and keep their prices constant instead of increasing prices to gain or maintain market share. Hysteresis effects, evidenced by Froot and Klemperer (1989), imply that a temporary loss in market share is likely to become permanent.

Second, quantity rigidities due to trade restrictions or because companies work close to or at full capacity imply that companies prefer to keep their prices

constant in the case of an appreciation, instead of decreasing it, to keep the demand constant (see Bussière (2007) and Knetter (1993))².

At an aggregate level, Taylor (2000) argued that the establishment of a strong nominal anchor in many countries has led to a low pass-through of exchange rate depreciation to inflation. Frankel, Parsley, and Wei (2005) supported this argument by showing that the less inflationary environment preferred by many central banks is an important determinant of a low pass-through after depreciations.

In the same vein, the business-cycle suggests that the ERPT is asymmetric in the consumer price index. In fact, if the devaluation takes place in the midst of a recession, then prices increase less than they would decrease after an appreciation. The resulting recession acts to depress domestic prices, hence implying that domestic prices do not respond much to exchange rate depreciation (Goldfain and Werlang (2000), Carranza and Gomez-Biscarri (2009)).

On the whole, the theoretical literature has identified possible reasons why the elasticity of prices to exchange rate changes may be asymmetric across appreciations and depreciations. Yet, only a small research effort has been devoted to analyse empirically this asymmetry of the ERPT. In the following, we review the few empirical evidence and the model specifications of existing studies.

2.2 Empirical evidence

A few micro-oriented studies focusing on a particular product or industry confirm the existence of asymmetric pass-through and point towards the influence of the competitive structure of the industry upon the direction of the asymmetry. For example, Campa and Sebastiá-Barriel (2006) examined non-linearities in the reactions of import prices using data from European Union countries at the industry level. They estimated the long-run relationship of import prices to exchange rates and foreign prices by relying on error correction representations and allowing the short-run adjustment in the deviation of prices from their equilibrium to be non-linear. They found that in manufacturing industries, exchange rate appreciations of the home currency experience a faster adjustment than those caused by depreciation, probably an attempt by foreign firms

²For example, such quantity constraints exist in chemical and petroleum industries (Bussière (2007)).

to maintain their market share. On the contrary, they found that a symmetric adjustment is possible in primary industries with homogenous products.

Yang (2007) examined import price data from 98 disaggregated industries in the US manufacturing sector and the import prices for all commodities. He observed the large changes in the value of the dollar during the 1980s to test for asymmetric responses in US import prices to dollar appreciations and dollar depreciations. He applied an Ordinary Least Squares model to log-differentiated data and included a dummy variable to distinguish between the period before and after March 1985, when the dollar reached its peak and then began to depreciate. In few industries, he found evidence of an asymmetric ERPT but the direction depended on the sector, a result that suggests that the competitive structure of the sector matters.

Pollard and Coughlin (2003) analyzed exchange rate pass-through in US import prices in 30 industries to examine whether the direction and the size of a change in the exchange rate affect the pass-through. They estimated a relationship between log-differentiated import prices and usual determinants and included two dummy variables that separate quarters in which the dollar appreciated from those in which it depreciated. In a second regression, they included two dummy variables that separated large and small changes in the exchange rate. They found evidence of asymmetric behavior in 15 industries, but not across manufacturing firms and they found that the direction of the asymmetry varied across industries.

Wickremasinghe and Silvapulle (2004) examined the exchange rate pass-through to import prices of manufactured goods in Japan using asymmetric unit root tests, cointegration tests and asymmetric models. They built on Webber (1999) to construct a new variable expressed as the accumulated sum of appreciation and depreciation episodes and included the series of depreciation episodes in the long-run exchange rate pass-through equation to test for cointegration. They found evidence of an asymmetric pass-through, with appreciations being passed through more often than depreciations to import prices.

Yet, only few empirical studies have explored the issue at an aggregated level. Webber (1999) examined the response of import prices in eight Asian countries. He modeled asymmetries as a partial decomposition that captured appreciation and depreciation forces. He found that in five out of seven countries in which an equilibrium import price relationship was found, the import prices did not

decrease after an appreciation as much as they increased after an appreciation. Later, Bussière (2007) examined import and export prices in the G7 economies using simple dynamic linear models augmented with non-linear terms. His specification related the change in the logs of export and import prices to foreign prices and the producer price index. In separate estimations, he included interaction dummy variables in positive and negative values of the exchange rate, as well as threshold dummy variables and polynomial functions. His results indicated that the direction of the asymmetries and the magnitude of the nonlinearities varied across countries. Finally, Nogueira and Leon-Ledesma (2008) examined ERPT in six countries under an inflation targeting monetary regime. They used smooth transition models to investigate several possible sources of these nonlinearities. Their results suggest that the sources of nonlinearities vary considerably across countries.

So far, the previous literature has examined either short-run or long-run asymmetric effects. In the following Section, we present our strategy, based on an asymmetric cointegrating ARDL model, to relax the symmetry assumption both in the short- and in the long-run.

3 Methodology

Our empirical setting to estimate ERPT to prices is a mark-up model in which the determinants of the price level, p_t , are captured in a cointegrating relationship featuring the equilibrium level to which prices tend to adjust after a shock. This approach is derived from the imperfect competition hypothesis and is a central piece in inflation modeling approaches³.

Under this framework, the domestic (log) general price level, p_t , is assumed to be a mark-up over total unit costs, which includes the (log) unit labor costs, ulc_t , the (log) exchange rate, s_t , and the (log) energy prices, oil_t , as in the following multiple cointegrating long-run regression:

$$p_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 s_t + \beta_2 oil_t + \beta_3 ulc_t + \varepsilon_t, \quad (1)$$

where the regressors s_t , oil and ulc are defined such that $\Delta s_t = v_t$, $\Delta oil_t = \eta_t$ and $\Delta ulc_t = \omega_t$ and ε_t , v_t , η_t and ω_t follow iid processes with zero means and

³The model was first proposed by de Brouwer and Gordon (1998) with Australian data. Other applications can be found in Hendry (2001) and Banerjee and Mizen (2007) among others.

finite variances and are independently distributed of one-another. Hence, the “pass-through” refers to the direct effect of the exchange rate on the CPI level and it is estimated as the coefficient on the exchange rate, β_1 .

Following Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011), suppose that the data-generating process for $z_t = (\varepsilon_t, v_t, \eta_t, \omega_t)$ follows the general p -th order stationary VAR model of the following form:

$$z_t = \sum_{i=1}^p \Phi_i z_{t-i} + \nu_t, \quad (2)$$

where $\Phi_i, i = 1, \dots, p$, are $(k+1) \times (k+1)$ matrices of unknown coefficients, ν_t is an $iid(0, \Sigma)$ process with Σ being a $(k+1) \times (k+1)$ positive definite matrix, and $Z_0 \equiv (z - p, \dots, z_0)$ is given. It can be shown that Equation (1) can be written as an error correction model (ECM), where the change in p_t (i.e., the inflation rate, defined as $\Delta p_t = p_t - p_{t-1}$) is related to the last period’s disequilibrium and any variations induced by a change in the determinants of prices as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_t = & \mu + \rho_p p_{t-1} + \rho_s s_{t-1} + \rho_o oil_{t-1} + \rho_u ulc_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \Psi'_i \Delta p_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p (\phi'_i \Delta s_{t-i} + \theta'_i \Delta oil_{t-i} + \chi'_i \Delta ulc_{t-i} + \gamma'_i gap_{t-i}) + \nu_t, \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where, focusing only on our variable of interest, $\rho_s = -\rho_p \beta_1$ and ν_t is an iid process⁴. In addition to the previously mentioned variables, we include the output gap (*gap*) in Eq. (3) as a short-run determinant in order to take into account the dynamics described in the Phillips curve framework (de Brouwer and Gordon (1998)). Equation (3) encompasses a range of economic models because it allows us to examine the dynamics of both prices and inflation in a single dynamic framework.

Notice that equation (3) is an equivalent transformation of an ARDL(p, q, q, q) model for y_t, s_t, oil and ulc , with $q = p + 1$ and the choice of an appropriate lag structure such that the model is free from residual serial correlation. The previous ARDL model, based on Phillips and Hansen (1991) and Pesaran, Smith, and Shin (1996), fully covers both the long- and short-run relationships of the variables tested.

⁴See Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011) for further details.

In addition, this approach has several interesting characteristics. First, the standard ECM is the original Engle-Granger two-step approach, which is likely to be less efficient than a one-step solution such as ours. Second, the cointegration test procedure, presented below, performs better on small samples than do most conventional multivariate cointegration procedures, which are useful with large samples only⁵. Third, the cointegration test procedure does not require the restrictive assumption that all the variables under study must be integrated on the same order. Indeed, if some of the variables in Eq. (3) are $I(0)$, the classical methods, such as the Johansen (1988) cointegration procedure, would yield misleading conclusions⁶. Notice, however, that if all the level regressors in Eq. (3) are $I(1)$, then this is a cointegration relationship by definition. Instead, if the equation mixes $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ variables, then there is evidence of a long-run relationship. Given that the ARDL model can combine $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ variables in a long-run relationship rather than in a cointegrating relationship, we view the "bounds test" methodology as the most appropriate in our context⁷.

This feature of the ARDL model is clearly an advantage over regular cointegrating models since regular cointegrating models are specified on the basis of a set of $I(1)$ regressors, involving a form of "pre-test bias" in which only the variables that are $I(1)$, or can be proxied by an $I(1)$ series, are allowed to enter the model. The fact that the ARDL model allows us to combine $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ series in the long-run relationship overcomes this concern and allows greater flexibility⁸.

More in detail, the symmetric cointegration, or "bounds test", can be performed with two operational tests. First, following Banerjee, Dolado, and Mestre (1998), if $\rho_p = 0$, Eq. (3) reduces to the regression involving only first differences, implying that there is no long-run relationship between the level variables. Therefore, the first test, denoted t_{BDM} , is performed with the t -statistic as follows:

$$t_{BDM} : H_0 : \rho_p = 0 \quad \text{against} \quad H_1 : \rho_p \neq 0$$

⁵See Pesaran et al. (1996) and Pesaran et al. (2001)

⁶A series of studies by Pesaran and Shin (1995a), Pesaran and Shin (1995b), Pesaran, et al. (1996) and Pesaran et al. (2001) argued that as long as both $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ series exist in a system, conventional cointegration tests might bias the results of the long-run equilibrium interactions among variables.

⁷In particular, unit root tests point to the stationarity of the unit labor cost (see Table 7 in the appendix).

⁸We thank the referee for pointing this out to us.

Second, as suggested by Pesaran, Smith, and Shin (1996) and Pesaran, Smith, and Shin (2001), the denominated F_{PSS} is based on an F-test on the joint null hypothesis that the coefficients on the level variables are jointly equal to zero:

$$F_{PSS} : H_0 : \rho_p = \rho_s = \rho_{oil} = \rho_{ulc} = 0$$

against

$$H_1 : \rho_p \neq 0, H_1 : \rho_s \neq 0, H_1 : \rho_{oil} \neq 0 \text{ and } H_1 : \rho_{ulc} \neq 0$$

Instead of the conventional critical values, this test involves two asymptotic critical value bounds, depending on the dimension and cointegration rank of the explanatory level variables. In particular, Pesaran, Smith, and Shin (2001) show that the critical values take on lower and upper bounds, depending on whether the level regressors are all $I(1)$ or $I(0)$. The critical values tabulated for these two scenarios provide critical bounds for all classifications, irrespective of whether the regressors are $I(0)$, $I(1)$ or mutually cointegrated. Indeed, if the computed statistic exceeds its respective upper critical values, then there is evidence of a long-run relationship regardless of the order of integration of the variables. If, in contrast, it is below, it is not possible to reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and if it lies between the bounds, conclusive inferences may still be drawn if all variables are known to be $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ ⁹.

3.1 Allowing for asymmetry in the ARDL Framework

As suggested by the theoretical literature, the previous symmetric linear combination (Eq. 3) of stochastic regressors might be overly restrictive. To address this issue, our solution is to adopt a nonlinear cointegrating ARDL (NARDL) model suggested by Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011). They analyze the long-run level relationship by allowing for asymmetries in the context of a nonlinear error correction model. Following Schorderet (2004) and Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011), the starting point consists of the decomposition of a time series s_t into its positive (s_t^+) and negative (s_t^-) partial sums. In our particular case, this corresponds to:

⁹Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011) address the use of Monte Carlo simulations to assess the finite sample performance of the F_{PSS} test showing that the test is mis-sized. They suggest either the use of a pragmatic approach to the selection of the value k , – the number of regressors entering the long-run relationship – or, preferably, the use of a resampling approach to derive accurate empirical p -values.

$$\mathbf{s}_t^+ = \sum_{j=1}^t \Delta s_j^+ = \sum_{j=1}^t \max(\Delta s_j, 0), \quad \mathbf{s}_t^- = \sum_{j=1}^t \Delta s_j^- = \sum_{j=1}^t \min(\Delta s_j, 0) \quad (4)$$

where Δs_t^+ and Δs_t^- are the partial sum processes of depreciations and appreciations, respectively¹⁰. Following Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011), Equation (3) can then be modified to allow for asymmetric cointegration, such that the specification becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_t = & \mu + \rho_p p_{t-1} + \rho_s^+ s_{t-1}^+ + \rho_s^- s_{t-1}^- + \rho_{oil} oil_{t-1} + \rho_{ulc} ulc_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \Psi'_i \Delta p_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^p (\phi_i^{+'} \Delta s_{t-i}^+ + \phi_i^{-'} \Delta s_{t-i}^- + \theta'_i \Delta oil_{t-i} + \chi'_i \Delta ulc_{t-i} + \gamma'_i gap_{t-i}) + v_t \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the variables are defined as in Equation (3) and the superscripts ‘+’ and ‘-’ denote positive and negative partial sums computed following the previously mentioned decomposition method. In (5), the relationship is defined to allow for cointegration between prices and the positive and negative components of the exchange rates, controlling for the remainder of the underlying variables.

Equation (5) creates the possibility that the process being modeled may exhibit asymmetries over both the short and the long run, only over the long run or only over the short run. Indeed, whereas the first part in the equation represents the long-run relationship, which can be evaluated by bounds testing following Pesaran, Smith, and Shin (2001), the second line contains the lags of the asymmetric exchange rate terms in the first differences – it is on this part of the equation that we focus when testing for short-run asymmetry.

In greater detail, as in the linear cointegration case, Equation (5) can be bounds tested for a long-run relationship among the variables. Indeed, Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011) suggest the following operational tests for the existence of an asymmetric (cointegrating) long-run relationship. Based on the error correction model, if $\rho_p = 0$, Eq. (5) reduces to the linear regression involving only first differences, therefore implying that there is no long-run asymmetric relationship between the levels of p_t , s_t^+ , s_t^- , oil_t and ulc_t . As in the symmetric case, this test can be performed either as t_{BDM} statistic testing $\rho_p = 0$ or as an

¹⁰We note that asymmetry in the response of prices to the other explanatory variables is also possible, though that is not the aim of the present study.

F_{PSS} test of the joint null hypothesis $\rho_p = \rho_s^+ = \rho_s^- = \rho_{oil} = \rho_{ulc} = 0$.

Having estimated the model defined in (5), it is now possible to compute the long-run multipliers of interest in the following way: $L_s^+ = \rho_s^+ / -\rho_p$, $L_s^- = \rho_s^- / -\rho_p$. Long-run symmetry can be tested by a Wald test, with symmetry implying $L_s^+ = L_s^-$.

Finally, symmetry over the short run can be tested by a two standard Wald tests: (i.) $\phi_{t-i}^{+'} = \phi_{t-i}^{-'}$ for all $i = 0, \dots, p$ or (ii.) $\sum_{i=1}^{q-1} \phi_{t-i}^{+'} = \sum_{i=1}^{q-1} \phi_{t-i}^{-'}$. That is, on the sum of each one of the dynamic coefficients associated with '+' and '-'.

3.1.1 Dynamic nonlinear multipliers

Provided that the long-run relationship is asymmetric (either in the short-run, in the long-run or in both), an interesting pattern of asymmetry that we can derive from the NARDL presented above is from the positive and negative dynamic multipliers associated with unit changes in s^+ and s^- , respectively:

$$\mathbf{m}_h^+ = \sum_{j=0}^h \frac{\partial p_{t+j}}{\partial s_t^+}, \mathbf{m}_h^- = \sum_{j=0}^h \frac{\partial p_{t+j}}{\partial s_t^-}, h = 0, 1, 2 \dots \quad (6)$$

By construction, as $h \rightarrow \infty$, $\mathbf{m}_h^+ \rightarrow L_s^+$ and $\mathbf{m}_h^- \rightarrow L_s^-$ where \mathbf{m}_h^+ and \mathbf{m}_h^- are the positive and negative asymmetric long-run coefficients, respectively, as defined before¹¹. As noticed by Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011), the multipliers allow us to observe asymmetric adjustment paths and/or duration of the disequilibrium, adding valuable information to the long- and short-run forms of asymmetry. As such, the multipliers capture patterns of adjustment from the initial equilibrium to the new equilibrium following an economic perturbation (i.e., a depreciation or appreciation). These multipliers are derived from the interaction of the impact and reaction asymmetries in conjunction with the error correction coefficient, ρ_p in Equation (5).

4 Data definitions

In the empirical analysis, we used quarterly data from the first quarter of 1980 (1980:1) to the third quarter of 2009 (2009:3) from four major developed coun-

¹¹See Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2011) for more details on the derivation of the dynamic multipliers.

tries, namely Japan, Germany, the United Kingdom and the United States¹². In Equations (3) and (5), the dependent variable is the consumer price index (CPI), which we obtained from International Financial Statistics. Regarding the explanatory variables, the exchange rate corresponds to the nominal effective exchange rate, with an increase (decrease) indicating a depreciation (appreciation) and extracted from the Bank of International Settlements (BIS).

Finally, the unit labor cost, the price of oil (in the local currency) and the output gap were also obtained from the IMF and the OECD's Economic Outlook data. All the variables were seasonally adjusted and expressed in logarithms (except the output gap).

5 Results

In this Section, we first report on the bounds cointegration test. We then estimate the ARDL model and carry out the Long- and short-run symmetry tests. Finally, we obtain the long-run and dynamic multipliers as described above.

First, concerning the cointegration tests, we applied both the t_{BDM} and the F_{PSS} bounds tests on the benchmark linear model (Eq.(3)) and on the different representations that allow for asymmetry¹³. In all, four cases are considered: (i) allowing for no asymmetry in the short or the long run (equivalent to Eq.(3)), (ii) allowing for long-run asymmetry but imposing short-run symmetry, (iii) allowing for short-run asymmetry but restricting the long run to have symmetric effects and, (iv) allowing for both short- and long-run asymmetry (equivalent to Eq. (5)).

The results from the bounds cointegration tests, presented in Table 1, clearly point to a valid long-run relationship between prices and the explanatory variables in the four countries. Indeed, the t_{BDM} and the F_{PSS} test statistics exceed their respective upper critical values in both the symmetric and the asymmetric models. The finding that prices are cointegrated with a combination of input prices confirms existing linear estimations for the countries of our sample¹⁴.

¹²Due to data availability, the analysis of Germany covers the period 1991:1 to 2009:3.

¹³Starting an ARDL(p,q,q) with $\max p = \max q = 4$, we proceeded with a general-to-specific approach to select the final specifications by dropping all insignificant stationary regressors.

¹⁴See Banerjee and Russell (2001) and Bowdler and Jansen (2007).

Table 1: **Bounds-Tests for a Long-Run Relationship.**

Country	Symmetric		Asymmetric	
	t_{BDM}	F_{PSS}	t_{BDM}	F_{PSS}
Japan	3.889**	12.239*	3.886*	8.257*
Germany	6.910*	12.490*	6.911*	17.583*
UK	4.660*	10.928*	4.662*	8.844*
USA	3.874**	8.803*	3.864*	15.701*

Notes: (a) t_{BDM} is the BDM t-statistic testing the null hypothesis $\rho = 0$ in Eqs. (3) and (5); (b) F_{PSS} denotes the PSS F-statistic testing the null hypothesis $\rho_p = \rho_s = \rho_{oil} = \rho_{ulc} = 0$ and $\rho_p = \rho_s^+ = \rho_s^- = \rho_{oil} = \rho_{ulc} = 0$ in Eqs. (3) and (5), respectively; (c) *(**) indicate cointegration at the 5% (10%) significance level.

Table (2) reports the estimated coefficients of the ARDL models. As shown in the Table, the symmetric model shows that there is a positive association between prices and the exchange rate, indicating that depreciations (appreciations) are associated with an increase (decrease) that is less than proportional to the consumer prices in all the countries except for Japan, where the non-significance of the long-run coefficients (L_s) indicates that the CPI is not sensitive to exchange rates in symmetric models.

Table 2: **Long-run estimates of the symmetric exchange rate pass-through**

	Symmetric ARDL		
	Variable	Coeff.	t -stat
Japan	L_s	-0.010	-0.16
Germany	L_s	0.163	2.22
UK	L_s	0.142	2.42
USA	L_s	0.146	3.07

Notes:(a) L_s is the long-run coefficient associated with the change of the exchange rates.

To check the relevance of the asymmetric model, we performed the Wald tests for short- and long-run symmetry. As seen in Table 3, long-run symmetry does not occur in the countries tested here as the statistic exceeds its upper critical value, except in the UK. This is an important result that suggests that linear models are mis-specified. Turning to the short-run dynamics, symmetry also does not occur in Germany, the United Kingdom and the United States. Based on these tests, the preferred models are long-run asymmetry and short-run symmetry for Japan, long-run symmetry and short-run asymmetry for the UK and long-run

and short-run asymmetry for the remaining countries¹⁵.

Table 3: **Short- and long-run symmetry tests**

Country	Short-run W_{SR}	Long-run W_{LR}
Japan	0.307(0.580)	17.831 (0.000)
Germany	3.673(0.062)	8.555 (0.000)
UK	4.734 (0.030)	0.668 (0.506)
USA	10.434 (0.001)	46.275 (0.000)

Notes: (a) W_{SR} is the Wald test for short run additive symmetry testing the null hypothesis $\sum_{i=1}^{q-1} \phi_{i-i}^+ = \sum_{i=1}^{q-1} \phi_{i-i}^-$ in Eq. (5); (b) W_{LR} denotes the Wald test for long-run symmetry testing the null hypothesis $L_s^+ = \rho_s^+ / -\rho_p = L_s^- = \rho_s^- / -\rho_p$ in Eq. (5); (c) p-values in parenthesis.

We proceed to the analysis of the asymmetric effects based on the estimation results reported in Table (4)¹⁶. It is important to note that, in most cases, allowing for asymmetry may increase both the significance and the magnitude of the pass-through as well as the speed of adjustment. In particular, whereas in the restricted symmetric model the estimated long-run coefficient for Japan is not statistically significant, it becomes significant once we allow for asymmetric effects of the exchange rate. Similarly, ERPT in the asymmetric model is significantly higher in the case of the United States. This important result underscores the importance of accurately specifying the long-run relationship.

The results in Table 4 suggest a single asymmetry direction: in the four countries, a depreciation is more clearly passed through to prices than is an appreciation, either in the long- or in the short-run or in both (see the asymmetric short-run effects in table 7). In this sense, it is important to remark that micro-oriented works using disaggregated data find evidence of asymmetric responses but no clear pattern concerning the direction: in some industries, a depreciation is more clearly passed to prices, while in others, it is an appreciation. Evidence from the aggregate asymmetry data is thus novel.

Indeed, the results indicate that prices increase following a weakening of the domestic currency, but the response to an appreciation is distinctly non-significant

¹⁵The short-run asymmetric test indicates the additive symmetric adjustment, which is more appropriate in a general-to-specific approach that is likely to result in the inclusion of heterogeneous lags of the positive and negative partial sum process.

¹⁶For the sake of space, we provide only the symmetric model together with the most suitable asymmetric model (according to the Wald test for short- and long-run asymmetry). We also present only the estimated long-run coefficients of the exchange rate. Results from the complete equations are presented in tables 6 and 7 in the appendix.

Table 4: **Long-run estimates of the asymmetric exchange rate pass-through**

	Asymmetric ARDL		
	Variable	Coeff.	<i>t</i> -stat
Japan	L_s^+	0.157	2.26
	L_s^-	0.050	1.00
Germany	L_s^+	0.122	2.61
	L_s^-	-0.035	-0.25
UK	$L_s^{(c)}$	0.135	2.04
USA	L_s^+	0.385	6.91
	L_s^-	-0.102	-1.01

Notes: (a) L_s^+ and L_s^- are the long-run coefficients associated with the positive (depreciation) or negative (appreciation) changes of exchange rates, respectively; (b) The asymmetric models presented correspond to short run symmetry and long-run asymmetry in the cases of Japan, long-run symmetry and short-run asymmetry for the UK and short and long-run symmetry for Germany and the USA.

(i.e., the estimated long-run coefficient of the negative component of the exchange rate, L_s^- , is not significant), except in the UK, where symmetry is not rejected in the long-run. This asymmetric effect is confirmed by the Wald test statistic, which clearly rejects linearity.

Effectively, as it can be seen, in the long-run, a depreciation of 10% causes consumer prices to rise between 1.2% and 1.6% in Japan, Germany and the UK compared to almost 4%. Appreciations, in turn, are not significant in the long-run. This result is important because it implies that the low ERPT in the USA as suggested in the literature, might be due to a failure to model long-run asymmetric effects of the exchange rate accurately.

Turning now to an analysis of short-run dynamics, as mentioned earlier, we find that the null hypothesis of additive short-run symmetry is firmly rejected in Germany, the UK and the US. The analysis of the dynamic multipliers supports this finding and provides interesting patterns of asymmetry provided that the long-run relationship is asymmetric. Indeed, the dynamic multipliers, presented in Figure 1, allow us to trace the evolution of prices in the wake of an exchange rate shock and paint a vivid picture of the dynamic process. In addition, as seen in the figure, the imposition of symmetry weakens both the short- and long-run ERPT.

This is especially true in the case of Japan, where the imposition of long-run symmetry restrictions fundamentally changes the shape of the dynamic multipliers, resulting in a mild response of prices to exchange rate shocks that tends to be insignificant after about two years. Yet, the asymmetric multipliers are able to capture a relatively important and persistent pass-through with a depreciation.

In Germany, the multipliers reveal that consumer prices respond rapidly and strongly to both negative and positive exchange rate variations in the very short run. Indeed, as can be seen in the figure, the short run effects are somehow ambiguous and the full adjustment to the new equilibrium is a relatively prolonged process. In the United Kingdom, depreciations (the positive component) has a relatively strong negative impact in the short run, but it quickly becomes positive, tending to their long-run value within a few quarters. In contrast, appreciations tend to be milder in the short-run, but more persistent and significant after a few quarters. In the long-run depreciations and appreciations are both passed to the final price in more or less the same magnitude. Finally, in the USA, whereas appreciations are not significant neither in the short nor in the long-run, prices react mildly to depreciations after a few quarters and they slowly converge to their long-run.

The fact that depreciations are more strongly transmitted to consumer prices than are appreciations either in the short or in the long-run in the four countries in this sample may imply that producers tend to absorb the appreciation in order to increase their mark-up, while they pass a part of a depreciation to consumers in order to limit the reduction of their mark-up. This pricing strategy is possible only if the market power of price-setters is large enough. In this sense, our result might suggest that imperfect competition effects dominate.

Summing-up, our estimation results contradict the general idea that the exchange rate has no noticeable impact on consumer prices. On the contrary, we present strong evidence of long-run asymmetry in the ERPT in retail prices. Indeed, we find that in all countries in the sample, depreciations pass through more strongly than do appreciations. Our estimation results support the idea that the exchange rate still has an impact on consumer prices. This result is in line with Campa and Goldberg (2006), who argue that consumption price sen-

Figure 1: Dynamic multipliers

sitivity to exchange rates has increased over the past decade, even if exchange rate pass-through into import prices has declined for some types of goods.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we developed a novel and simple method of combining asymmetric cointegration with a dynamically flexible ARDL model to explore exchange rate pass-through in four major economies during the period 1980:1-2009:3. Our results suggest that there is clearly a role for the exchange rate in the determination of prices in the long run, even if exchange rate changes are less than completely associated with changes in consumer prices. At the same time, the responsiveness of prices to exchange rate variations is not linear. In particular, the pass-through of the exchange rate is lower after an appreciation than after a depreciation. In other words, domestic prices rise more as a result of domestic currency depreciation compared with how they fall as a result of a domestic currency appreciation. Following conclusions drawn in the theoretical literature, we have interpreted this result as a signal of weak market competition and downward price rigidities. To obtain more subtle conclusion regarding the structure of the competition and the asymmetric pass-through, micro-economic pricing behavior would be of central interest. For such an analysis, disaggregated, industry-level data are surely more informative.

Second, our modeling strategy estimates higher pass-through coefficients than do several past studies. This important result underscores the importance of accurately specifying the long-run relationship. The finding of a declining ERPT in previous studies may be due to mis-specifications related to the restricting symmetry assumption. Our result is in line with the recent conclusions of Goldberg and Campa (2010) who argue that the use of imported inputs in production has grown sharply since the mid-1990s, increasing the sensitivity to exchange rates of the production costs of final goods. We contributed to the literature by showing that this pass-through actually holds after depreciations.

Finally, the estimated importance of the asymmetric effect exerted by the nominal exchange rate may pose important dilemmas for policy-makers wishing to achieve both price stability and export competitiveness. Indeed, an important policy implication of these findings is that the differing dependence of the exchange rate pass-through on positive and negative changes should be taken into account in determining monetary policy rules. An open question remains regarding if prices respond differently depending on the magnitude of the exchange

rate variation. In terms of the modeling strategy, this might be examined by allowing the threshold to be different from zero. This is an issue that warrants further study.

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Appendix

Table 5: **Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root tests.**

		p	s	oil	ulc	s^+	s^-
Japan	Stat	2.80	-1.12	-2.59	-3.64	-2.79	-2.65
	prob.	0.05	0.70	0.09	0.00	0.20	0.25
Germany	Stat	2.13	-1.03	-2.05	-2.54	1.08	-1.70
	prob.	0.51	0.73	0.56	0.30	0.71	0.73
UK	Stat	-2.25	-1.73	-2.49	-3.33	-0.48	-2.40
	prob.	0.18	0.41	0.11	0.01	0.88	0.37
USA	Stat	-2.37	-2.44	-2.39	-6.47	-2.55	-2.91
	prob.	0.14	0.35	0.14	0.00	0.30	0.15

Notes: (a) Lags in the ADF test are chosen according to the Schwarz Information criterium, allowing for a maximum lag length of 4; (b) All the variables are defined as in Eqs. (3) and (5).

Table 6: Symmetric ARDL models.

Var.	Germany		Japan		UK		USA	
	Coeff.	t-value	Coeff.	t-value	Coeff.	t-value	Coeff.	t-value
μ	0.377	3.36	0.292	3.29	0.373	4.16	0.282	3.39
p_{t-1}	-0.137	-6.91	-0.063	-3.89	-0.097	-4.66	-0.073	-3.87
s_{t-1}	0.022	2.14	-0.001	-0.16	0.014	2.29	0.011	3.39
oil_{t-1}	0.014	5.64	-	-	0.004	3.43	0.003	3.27
ulc_{t-1}	0.022	1.21	0.028	3.12	0.086	4.13	0.075	3.24
Δp_{t-1}	-0.339	-3.49	-0.224	-2.95	0.339	4.23	-	-
Δp_{t-2}	-0.176	-1.72	-	-	-	-	-	-
Δp_{t-3}	-0.282	-3.01	-0.206	-2.70	-	-	0.259	4.55
Δp_{t-4}	0.291	3.03	0.344	4.91	-0.138	-2.26	-	-
Δs_t	0.060	2.06	-	-	-	-	-	-
Δs_{t-1}	-	-	0.016	1.85	-0.028	-2.29	-	-
Δs_{t-2}	-0.103	-3.34	-	-	-	-	-	-
Δs_{t-3}	-	-	0.017	1.96	-0.025	-2.00	-	-
Δs_{t-4}	-0.059	-1.81	0.017	1.80	-0.023	-1.88	-0.021	-1.77
Δoil_t	0.015	5.72	0.004	1.44	0.007	2.89	0.023	10.37
Δoil_{t-1}	-	-	0.010	3.69	-	-	-	-
Δoil_{t-2}	-0.010	-2.84	0.008	2.56	-	-	0.005	1.86
Δoil_{t-3}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Δoil_{t-4}	-0.011	-2.84	0.010	3.49	-	-	-	-
Δulc_t	-0.158	-3.30	-	-	-	-	-	-
Δulc_{t-1}	-	-	0.339	2.21	-	-	-	-
Δulc_{t-2}	-0.170	-2.31	-0.329	-2.12	0.118	2.25	-	-
Δulc_{t-3}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Δulc_{t-4}	-0.176	-2.86	-	-	-	-	-	-
gap_t	-	-	-0.001	-2.54	-	-	-	-
gap_{t-1}	-	-	0.001	2.15	-0.001	-3.16	0.001	5.30
gap_{t-2}	-	-	0.004	2.50	-	-	-	-
gap_{t-3}	-	-	-0.007	-2.65	0.004	4.61	-	-
gap_{t-4}	0.002	4.52	0.004	2.43	-0.002	-2.58	-	-

Notes: (a) Lags in the ARDL models are chosen according to a general-to-specific procedure, allowing for a maximum lag length of 4; (b) All the variables are defined as in Eqs. (3).

Table 7: **Asymmetric ARDL models.**

Germany			Japan			UK			USA		
Var.	Coeff.	t-value									
μ	0.82	4.27	μ	0.48	3.42	μ	0.31	3.77	μ	0.21	3.49
p_{t-1}	-0.22	-5.41	p_{t-1}	-0.10	-3.75	p_{t-1}	-0.08	-4.20	p_{t-1}	-0.05	-3.96
s_{t-1}^+	-0.01	-0.24	s_{t-1}^+	0.02	2.68	s_{t-1}	0.01	1.94	s_{t-1}^+	0.02	3.66
s_{t-1}^-	0.03	2.80	s_{t-1}^-	0.01	1.22	-	-	-	s_{t-1}^-	-0.01	-0.82
oil_{t-1}	0.02	6.27	oil_{t-1}	0.00	-2.77	oil_{t-1}	0.00	2.89	oil_{t-1}	0.00	1.72
ulc_{t-1}	0.03	1.82	ulc_{t-1}	0.04	2.00	ulc_{t-1}	0.07	3.70	ulc_{t-1}	-	-
Δp_{t-1}	-0.33	-3.62	Δp_{t-1}	-0.28	-3.83	Δp_{t-1}	0.37	4.63	Δp_{t-1}	-	-
Δp_{t-2}	-0.37	-3.82	Δp_{t-2}	-	-	Δp_{t-2}	-	-	Δp_{t-2}	-	-
Δp_{t-3}	-0.47	-5.23	Δp_{t-3}	-0.20	-2.60	Δp_{t-3}	-	-	Δp_{t-3}	0.23	3.87
Δp_{t-4}	0.25	2.82	Δp_{t-4}	0.29	3.92	Δp_{t-4}	-	-	Δp_{t-4}	-	-
Δs_t^+	-	-	Δs_t	-	-	Δs_t^+	-	-	Δs_t^+	-	-
Δs_{t-1}^+	-0.11	-2.21	Δs_{t-1}	0.01	1.41	Δs_{t-1}^+	-0.05	-2.76	Δs_{t-1}^+	-	-
Δs_{t-2}^+	-0.17	-3.28	Δs_{t-2}	-	-	Δs_{t-2}^+	-	-	Δs_{t-2}^+	-0.05	-2.57
Δs_{t-3}^+	-	-	Δs_{t-3}	0.01	1.05	Δs_{t-3}^+	-0.03	-1.94	Δs_{t-3}^+	-	-
Δs_{t-4}^+	-	-	Δs_{t-4}	-	-	Δs_{t-4}^+	-	-	Δs_{t-4}^+	-	-
Δs_t^-	0.12	2.88	-	-	-	Δs_t^-	-	-	Δs_t^-	-	-
Δs_{t-1}^-	-	-	-	-	-	Δs_{t-1}^-	-	-	Δs_{t-1}^-	-	-
Δs_{t-2}^-	-	-	-	-	-	Δs_{t-2}^-	-	-	Δs_{t-2}^-	0.05	2.28
Δs_{t-3}^-	-0.14	-2.92	-	-	-	Δs_{t-3}^-	-	-	Δs_{t-3}^-	-	-
Δs_{t-4}^-	-0.12	-2.53	-	-	-	Δs_{t-4}^-	-	-	Δs_{t-4}^-	-	-
Δoil_t	0.02	5.93	Δoil_t	-	-	Δoil_t	0.01	3.24	Δoil_t	0.02	10.23
Δoil_{t-1}	-	-	Δoil_{t-1}	0.01	4.28	Δoil_{t-1}	-	-	Δoil_{t-1}	-	-
Δoil_{t-2}	-0.01	-3.03	Δoil_{t-2}	0.01	3.29	Δoil_{t-2}	-	-	Δoil_{t-2}	0.01	2.24
Δoil_{t-3}	-	-									
Δoil_{t-4}	-0.01	-3.61	Δoil_{t-4}	0.01	3.49	Δoil_{t-4}	-	-	Δoil_{t-4}	-	-
Δulc_t	-	-									
Δulc_{t-1}	-0.32	-5.70	Δulc_{t-1}	-	-	Δulc_{t-1}	-	-	Δulc_{t-1}	-	-
Δulc_{t-2}	-	-	Δulc_{t-2}	0.40	2.91	Δulc_{t-2}	0.12	1.98	Δulc_{t-2}	-	-
Δulc_{t-3}	-0.33	-4.62	Δulc_{t-3}	-0.29	-1.97	Δulc_{t-3}	-	-	Δulc_{t-3}	-	-
Δulc_{t-4}	-	-									
gap_t	0.00	-2.75	gap_t	-	-	gap_t	0.00	-2.71	gap_t	-	-
gap_{t-1}	0.00	3.34	gap_{t-1}	-	-	gap_{t-1}	-	-	gap_{t-1}	0.00	2.32
gap_{t-2}	-	-	gap_{t-2}	0.01	3.94	gap_{t-2}	-	-	gap_{t-2}	-	-
gap_{t-3}	-	-	gap_{t-3}	-0.01	-3.07	gap_{t-3}	0.00	4.68	gap_{t-3}	-	-
gap_{t-4}	0.00	5.65	gap_{t-4}	0.00	2.50	gap_{t-4}	0.00	-3.04	gap_{t-4}	-	-

Notes: (a) Lags in the ARDL models are chosen according to a general-to-specific procedure, allowing for a maximum lag length of 4; (b) All the variables are defined as in Eqs. (5).